

Cardiometabolic risk factors for admission to the intensive care unit

Factores de riesgo cardiometabólicos para el ingreso en la unidad de cuidados intensivos

Fernanda Telenchana MD^{1*} <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-1662-5920>

Raúl Telenchana MD¹ <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0477-3069>

Alicia Morocho MgSc² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7860-8011>

Catherine Parra MD¹ <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-6598-5136>

Tamara Cárdenas MgSc³ <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-8481-6052>

Belkys Navarro MgSc³ <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4207-5712>

Vanessa Cobos MgSc³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3216-9738>

Moisés Cajías MgSc³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3306-2991>

¹Centro Latinoamericano de Estudios Epidemiológicos y Salud Social, Cuenca, Ecuador.

²Universidad Católica de Cuenca, Grupo de Investigación, Salud, Ciencia, Innovación "ISCI", Cuenca, Ecuador

³Universidad Bolivariana del Ecuador, Guayas, Ecuador.

***Autor de correspondencia:** Fernanda Telenchana, MD. Centro Latinoamericano de Estudios Epidemiológicos y Salud Social, Cuenca, Ecuador.

Correo electrónico: ferelyth_88@hotmail.com

Received: 07/20/2025 Accepted: 09/19/2025 Published: 11/12/2025 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17616828>

630

Abstract

The increasing prevalence of cardiometabolic conditions like hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and obesity is a major public health concern.

These conditions are linked to several complications and comorbidities associated with hospital admission, longer length of stay, and higher healthcare costs. It has been proven that cardiometabolic risk factors (CMRF) are tightly linked to poorer clinical outcomes and higher mortality rates. However, assessing whether their impact on intensive care unit (ICU) admission is significant is a matter of debate. Although the prevalence of CMRF in the ICU is indeed significantly higher than that of the general population, no studies have been able to establish them as independent risk factors for ICU admission outside the context of COVID-19 cases. On the other hand, CMRF increase the prevalence of life-threatening conditions like congestive heart failure, chronic kidney disease, acute myocardial infarction, stroke, and many other entities that are indeed correlated with ICU admission. Nonetheless, the attributable risk for ICU admission in these cases may lie in the complications, and not the underlying CMRF properly. This review aims to analyze the evidence regarding the impact of CMRF on the rates of ICU admission to assess their utility as predictive factors for ICU hospitalization.

Keywords: Cardiometabolic risk factors, cardiovascular disease, intensive care unit, critical care, predictive factors.

Resumen

El aumento de la prevalencia de las afecciones cardiometabólicas, como la hipertensión, la diabetes mellitus y la obesidad, representa un importante problema de salud pública. Estas condiciones se asocian con múltiples complicaciones y comorbilidades relacionadas con la hospitalización, una mayor duración de la estancia y un incremento en los costos sanitarios. Se ha demostrado que los factores de riesgo cardiometabólicos (FRCM) están estrechamente vinculados con peores resultados clínicos y mayores tasas de mortalidad. Sin embargo, aún existe debate sobre si su impacto en el ingreso a la unidad de cuidados intensivos (UCI) es realmente significativo. Aunque la prevalencia de los FRCM en la UCI es considerablemente mayor que en la población general, ningún estudio ha logrado establecerlos como factores de riesgo independientes para el ingreso en UCI fuera del contexto de los casos de COVID-19. Por otro lado, los FRCM aumentan la prevalencia de enfermedades potencialmente mortales como la insuficiencia cardíaca congestiva, la enfermedad renal crónica, el infarto agudo de miocardio, el accidente cerebrovascular y muchas otras entidades que sí se correlacionan con el ingreso en UCI. No obstante, el riesgo atribuible de ingreso en UCI en estos casos podría deberse a las complicaciones derivadas y no propiamente a los FRCM subyacentes. Esta revisión tiene como objetivo analizar la evidencia disponible sobre el impacto de los FRCM en las tasas de ingreso en

UCI, con el fin de evaluar su utilidad como factores predictivos de hospitalización en cuidados intensivos.

Palabras clave: factores de riesgo cardiometabólicos, enfermedad cardiovascular, unidad de cuidados intensivos, cuidados críticos, factores predictivos.

Introduction

During the last century, the leading causes of death have significantly evolved. Infectious diseases went from being the leading cause of death to one of the most preventable causes. Instead, chronic noncommunicable diseases have occupied their place¹. Conditions like cancer, diabetes mellitus (DM), hypertension (HT), heart failure, chronic pulmonary disease, chronic kidney disease (CKD), and many others have replaced infectious diseases as the most relevant causes of death worldwide². Among these conditions, cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are the leading cause of global mortality and the major contributor to disability³. The prevalence of CVD has nearly doubled from 271 million in 1990 to 523 million in 2019. Likewise, CVD-attributable deaths have steadily risen from 12 million to 18.6 million in the same period⁴.

The increased prevalence of CVD is partly explained by the parallel growth in cardiometabolic risk factors (CMRF). Obesity, DM, HT, dyslipidemia, metabolic syndrome, and other risk factors like smoking, physical inactivity and unhealthy dietary patterns have exponentially grown to pandemic proportions in the last decades⁵. Consequently, there is a growing concern in the medical community regarding the impact of these conditions on the quality of life and life expectancy in patients with CMRF⁶. These factors increase the risk of developing life-threatening conditions like acute myocardial infarction (AMI), stroke, pulmonary embolism, and sepsis^{7,8}. In light of the severity of these conditions, it is expected that these patients may need admission to an intensive care unit (ICU)⁹.

The rate of admission to the ICU varies according to the triggering condition. However, the risk of needing ICU admission increases as more risk factors are associated with the profile of the patients¹⁰. Variables like age, renal function, hematologic parameters, and prior history of chronic diseases increase the likelihood of needing critical care in specific situations. Moreover, most of these factors also increase the likelihood of in-hospital death^{11,12}. Several scales, like the Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA), have long been used as

screening tools to estimate the severity of patients' condition at a certain point in time, and thus estimate the need for ICU admission¹³. However, most available scales do not consider CMRF for their predictive accuracy. This review aims to analyze the evidence regarding the impact of CMRF on the rates of ICU admission to assess their utility as predictive factors for ICU hospitalization.

CARDIOMETABOLIC RISK FACTORS AND INTENSIVE CARE UNIT ADMISSION: FACT OR FICTION?

HT is the leading preventable risk factor for CVD and all-cause mortality worldwide. Nearly 1.4 billion people suffered from HT in 2010, with a tendency to rise in the near future¹⁴. As a result, HT is a frequent comorbidity in hospitalized patients. However, it is rarely the cause of hospital admission, and rather, it is most often a secondary diagnosis¹⁵. Although patients with hypertensive crises may need in-hospital management, these patients represent a small proportion of the hypertensive population, of less than 5 per 1000 patients with diagnosed HT¹⁶. Nevertheless, HT is known for significantly increasing the risk of AMI, stroke, and other conditions that require in-hospital management and, sometimes, ICU admission¹⁷.

It has been demonstrated that HT increases the rate of hospital admission, the cost of hospitalization, and the length of stay, independently of the reason for hospitalization¹⁸. Recently, HT was labeled a risk factor for ICU admission due to the analyses regarding hospitalization in patients with Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19)¹⁹. A plethora of studies showed HT was strongly associated with critical cases of COVID-19 and, thus, ICU admission. For instance, Du et al.²⁰ analyzed 24 observational studies. They concluded that the risk of ICU admission in COVID-19 patients was significantly higher than that of the patients without HT (Odds ratio (OR): 1.82). The authors concluded HT was independently associated with developing critical COVID-19, ICU admission, and in-hospital mortality from COVID-19.

Several authors and meta-analyses have reported the same findings from different locations, further reassuring the impact of HT on ICU admission rates²¹⁻²⁶. Nonetheless, other studies have failed to find an association between HT and ICU admission in the context of other diseases. Moreover, Nystrom et al.²⁷ reported that patients with high blood pressure (BP) at the time of admission to the ICU in patients with AMI had a better prognosis than those with lower BP values. This raises questions regarding the relationship between BP and mortality in a situation of acute stress²⁸. Similarly, PROVE-IT-TIMI 22 trial proved that HT was independently associated with an increased risk of future cardiovascular events, but not with an increased need for intensive care²⁹.

Conversely, the INTERACT2 trial analyzed several variables associated with ICU admission in patients with acute cerebral hemorrhage. Analyses showed that younger age, large hemorrhage volume, and high sys-

tolic BP on admission were associated with an increased rate of admission to the ICU. Likewise, prior history of antihypertensive treatment, and therefore a history of HT, was associated with an increased risk of ICU admission and prolonged length of stay³⁰. Likewise, Knight et al.³¹ analyzed the risk factors associated with unexpected ICU admission in patients undergoing elective non-cardiac and non-transplant major surgical procedures. Although HT did not show an independent correlation with ICU admission, clinical surrogates did. Patients with CKD, valvular heart disease, peripheral vascular disease, and congestive heart failure (CHF) had a significantly greater risk of unexpected ICU admission³¹. However, more research is needed regarding the impact of HT as an independent factor for ICU admission in several different contexts to provide suitable conclusions.

On the other hand, type 2 DM (DM2) is another chronic noncommunicable condition known for its multiple comorbidities. Moreover, DM2 significantly increases the risk of life-threatening conditions like AMI, stroke, diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA), CKD, CHF, and many others^{32,33}. As a result, studies have shown that ICU admissions are more prevalent in patients with DM2 than in those without (5% vs. 3.3%, $P < 0.001$)³⁴. Similar to HT, observational studies from COVID-19 populations concluded that diabetic status, independent of the type, was tightly correlated with critical COVID-19, ICU admission, and in-hospital mortality³⁵. Diabetic patients had nearly triple the risk of needing ICU admission compared to non-diabetic individuals (OR: 2.79, 95% CI; 1.85-4.22)³⁶. Likewise, other studies reported that glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) greater than 7% was significantly associated with ICU admission in COVID-19 patients³⁷.

However, there is scarce evidence regarding DM2 as an independent risk factor for ICU admission after adjusting for DM complications and comorbidities³⁸. Conversely, evidence has shown that hyperglycemia at the moment of admission is significantly associated with ICU admission rates and mortality prognosis³⁹⁻⁴². Since hyperglycemia is part of the normal acute stress response, it is often difficult to distinguish pure stress hyperglycemia from decompensated diabetic status or a combination of both. Calculating stress hyperglycemia parameters like stress hyperglycemia ratio (SHR) offer an alternative to distinguish between these entities^{43,44}. Other glycemic parameters like glycemic gap, SHR, and glycemic variability have also been linked to increased ICU admission and poorer outcomes⁴⁵. More importantly, stress hyperglycemia has more evidence regarding increased ICU admission and worse outcome than DM⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹. As a result, more research is needed to establish the independent role of DM in ICU admission.

Regarding obesity, increasing evidence has shown that the prevalence of obesity inside ICU facilities has increased in the past decades. Obesity prevalence inside the ICU has been reported to be between 28.2% and 36%, similar to the prevalence of the general popula-

tion⁵⁰. However, there is still debate regarding the impact of obesity on hospitalization outcomes. In hospitalized ICU patients with obesity and chronic illnesses, overweight and moderate obesity have a protective effect against mortality compared to normal body mass index (BMI) and severe obesity, a phenomenon termed the obesity paradox⁵¹. However, despite the protection against mortality, morbidity is adversely affected by obesity, with a linear correlation between BMI and in-hospital complications⁵². Although an important correlation between obesity and critical COVID-19 has been demonstrated, as with the previous risk factors, it has not been possible to reproduce those results outside the context of COVID-19⁵³⁻⁵⁵.

Conclusions

The increasing prevalence of cardiometabolic conditions like HT, DM, and obesity is a major public health concern. These conditions are linked to several complications and comorbidities associated with hospital admission, longer length of stay, and higher healthcare costs. It has been proven that CMRF are tightly linked to poorer clinical outcomes and higher mortality rates. However, assessing whether their impact on ICU admission is significant is a matter of debate. Although the prevalence of CMRF in the ICU is indeed significantly higher than that of the general population, no studies have been able to establish them as independent risk factors for ICU admission outside the context of COVID-19 cases. On the other hand, CMRF increase the prevalence of life-threatening conditions like CHF, CKD, AMI, stroke, and many other entities that are indeed correlated with ICU admission. Nonetheless, the attributable risk for ICU admission in these cases lies in the complications, not the underlying CMRF. Multivariate analyses adjusting for confounders and complications are needed to establish the independent role of CMRF as predictors of ICU admission. Given the lack of evidence, at present, CMRF may not increase the accuracy of ICU admission criteria.

References

1. Santosa A, Wall S, Fottrell E, Högberg U, Byass P. The development and experience of epidemiological transition theory over four decades: a systematic review. *Glob Health Action*. 2014 May 15;7:10.3402/gha.v7.23574.
2. Forouzanfar MH, Afshin A, Alexander LT, Anderson HR, Bhutta ZA, Biryukov S, et al. Global, regional, and national comparative risk assessment of 79 behavioural, environmental and occupational, and metabolic risks or clusters of risks, 1990–2015: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2015. *The Lancet*. 2016 Oct 8;388(10053):1659–724.
3. Lozano R, Naghavi M, Foreman K, Lim S, Shibuya K, Aboyans V, et al. Global and regional mortality from 235 causes of death for 20 age groups in 1990 and 2010: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010. *Lancet Lond Engl*. 2012 Dec 15;380(9859):2095–128.
4. Roth GA, Mensah GA, Johnson CO, Addolorato G, Ammirati E, Badour LM, et al. Global Burden of Cardiovascular Diseases and Risk Factors, 1990–2019: Update From the GBD 2019 Study. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2020 Dec 22;76(25):2982–3021.
5. Miranda JJ, Carrillo-Larco RM, Ferreccio C, Hambleton IR, Lotufo PA, Nieto-Martínez R, et al. Trends in cardiometabolic risk factors in the Americas between 1980 and 2014: a pooled analysis of population-based surveys. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2020 Jan 1;8(1):e123–33.
6. Pogodina A, Rychkova L, Kravtsova O, Klimkina J, Kosovtzeva A. Cardiometabolic Risk Factors and Health-Related Quality of Life in Adolescents with Obesity. *Child Obes*. 2017 Dec;13(6):499–506.
7. Braffett BH, Bebu I, El ghormli L, Cowie CC, Sivitz WI, Pop-Busui R, et al. Cardiometabolic Risk Factors and Incident Cardiovascular Disease Events in Women vs Men With Type 1 Diabetes. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2022 Sep 8;5(9):e2230710.
8. Bakhtiyari M, Kazemian E, Kabir K, Hadaegh F, Aghajanian S, Mardi P, et al. Contribution of obesity and cardiometabolic risk factors in developing cardiovascular disease: a population-based cohort study. *Sci Rep*. 2022 Jan 28;12(1):1544.
9. Cook DJ, Webb S, Proudfoot A. Assessment and management of cardiovascular disease in the intensive care unit. *Heart*. 2022 Mar;108(5):397–405.
10. Boerma LM, Reijnders EPJ, Hessels RAPA, V Hooft MAA. Risk factors for unplanned transfer to the intensive care unit after emergency department admission. *Am J Emerg Med*. 2017 Aug;35(8):1154–8.
11. Naqvi IH, Mahmood K, Ziaullah S, Kashif SM, Sharif A. Better prognostic marker in ICU - APACHE II, SOFA or SAP III? *Pak J Med Sci*. 2016;32(5):1146–51.
12. Pellathy TP, Pinsky MR, Hravnak M. ICU Scoring Systems. *Crit Care Nurse*. 2021 Aug 1;41(4):54–64.
13. Lambden S, Laterre PF, Levy MM, Francois B. The SOFA score—development, utility and challenges of accurate assessment in clinical trials. *Crit Care*. 2019 Nov 27;23(1):374.
14. Mills KT, Stefanescu A, He J. The global epidemiology of hypertension. *Nat Rev Nephrol*. 2020 Apr;16(4):223–37.
15. WANG G, FANG J, AYALA C. Hypertension-associated hospitalizations and costs in the United States, 1979–2006. *Blood Press*. 2014 Apr;23(2):126–33.
16. Pinna G, Pascale C, Fornengo P, Arras S, Piras C, Panzarasa P, et al. Hospital Admissions for Hypertensive Crisis in the Emergency Departments: A Large Multicenter Italian Study. *PLoS ONE*. 2014 Apr 2;9(4):e93542.
17. Kjeldsen SE. Hypertension and cardiovascular risk: General aspects. *Pharmacol Res*. 2018 Mar;129:95–9.
18. Dantas RC de O, da Silva JPT, Dantas DC de O, Roncalli ÂG. Factors associated with hospital admissions due to hypertension. *Einstein*. 2018 Sep 11;16(3):eAO4283.
19. Qian Z, Li Z, Peng J, Gao Q, Cai S, Xu X. Association between hypertension and prognosis of patients with COVID-19: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Exp Hypertens N Y N* 1993. 2022 Jul 4;44(5):451–8.
20. Du Y, Zhou N, Zha W, Lv Y. Hypertension is a clinically important risk factor for critical illness and mortality in COVID-19: A meta-analysis. *Nutr Metab Cardiovasc Dis*. 2021 Mar 10;31(3):745–55.
21. Geng L, He C, Kan H, Zhang K, Mao A, Zhang C, et al. The association between blood pressure levels and mortality in critically ill patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a case-series report. *Hypertens Res*. 2021 Mar;44(3):368–70.
22. Roncon L, Zuin M, Zuliani G, Rigatelli G. Patients with arterial hypertension and COVID-19 are at higher risk of ICU admission. *BJA Br J Anaesth*. 2020 Aug;125(2):e254–5.
23. Xiong TY, Huang FY, Liu Q, Peng Y, Xu YN, Wei JF, et al. Hypertension is a risk factor for adverse outcomes in patients with coronavirus disease 2019: a cohort study. *Ann Med*. 2020 Oct 2;52(7):361–6.
24. Kim L, Garg S, O'Halloran A, Whitaker M, Pham H, Anderson EJ, et al. Risk Factors for Intensive Care Unit Admission and In-hospital Mortality Among Hospitalized Adults Identified through the US Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19)-Associated Hospitalization Surveillance Network (COVID-NET). *Clin Infect Dis Off Publ Infect Dis Soc Am*. 2021 May 4;72(9):e206–14.
25. Shayganfar A, Sami R, Sadeghi S, Dehghan M, Khademi N, Rikhtehgaran R, et al. Risk factors associated with intensive care unit (ICU) admission and in-hospital death among adults hospitalized with COVID-19: a two-center retrospective observational study in tertiary care hospitals. *Emerg Radiol*. 2021 Aug 1;28(4):691–7.
26. McFarlane E, Linschoten M, Asselbergs FW, Lacy PS, Jedrzejewski D, Williams B. The impact of pre-existing hypertension and its treatment on outcomes in patients admitted to hospital with COVID-19. *Hypertens Res*. 2022 May;45(5):834–45.
27. Nystrom F, Wijkman M, Fredriksson M, Stenestrand U. HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE AT ADMISSION TO THE INTENSIVE CARE UNIT FOR CHEST PAIN CONFERS A LOW LONG-TERM TOTAL MORTALITY: PP.15.68. *J Hypertens*. 2010 Jun;28:e269.
28. Picariello C, Lazzeri C, Attanà P, Chiostrì M, Gensini GF, Valente S. The Impact of Hypertension on Patients with Acute Coronary Syndromes. *Int J Hypertens*. 2011 Jun 22;2011:563657.
29. Bangalore S, Qin J, Sloan S, Murphy SA, Cannon CP, PROVE IT-TIMI 22 Trial Investigators. What is the optimal blood pressure in patients after acute coronary syndromes?: Relationship of blood pressure and cardiovascular events in the PRavastatin OR atorvastatin Evaluation and Infection Therapy-Thrombolysis In Myocardial Infarction (PROVE IT-TIMI) 22 trial. *Circulation*. 2010 Nov 23;122(21):2142–51.
30. Wartenberg KE, Wang X, Muñoz-Venturelli P, Rabinstein AA, Lavados PM, Anderson CS, et al. Intensive Care Unit Admission for Patients in the INTERACT2 ICH Blood Pressure Treatment Trial:

- Characteristics, Predictors, and Outcomes. *Neurocrit Care*. 2017 Jun;26(3):371–8.
31. Knight JB, Lebovitz EE, Gelzinis TA, Hilmi IA. Preoperative risk factors for unexpected postoperative intensive care unit admission: A retrospective case analysis. *Anaesth Crit Care Pain Med*. 2018 Dec;37(6):571–5.
 32. Teck J. Diabetes-Associated Comorbidities. *Prim Care*. 2022 Jun;49(2):275–86.
 33. Ma CX, Ma XN, Guan CH, Li YD, Mauricio D, Fu SB. Cardiovascular disease in type 2 diabetes mellitus: progress toward personalized management. *Cardiovasc Diabetol*. 2022 May 14;21(1):74.
 34. Osuagwu UL, Xu M, Piya MK, Agho KE, Simmons D. Factors associated with long intensive care unit (ICU) admission among inpatients with and without diabetes in South Western Sydney public hospitals using the New South Wales admission patient data collection (2014–2017). *BMC Endocr Disord*. 2022 Jan 20;22(1):27.
 35. Kastora S, Patel M, Carter B, Delibegovic M, Myint PK. Impact of diabetes on COVID-19 mortality and hospital outcomes from a global perspective: An umbrella systematic review and meta-analysis. *Endocrinol Diabetes Metab*. 2022 May;5(3):e00338.
 36. Roncon L, Zuin M, Rigatelli G, Zuliani G. Diabetic patients with COVID-19 infection are at higher risk of ICU admission and poor short-term outcome. *J Clin Virol Off Publ Pan Am Soc Clin Virol*. 2020 Jun;127:104354.
 37. Lei M, Lin K, Pi Y, Huang X, Fan L, Huang J, et al. Clinical Features and Risk Factors of ICU Admission for COVID-19 Patients with Diabetes. *J Diabetes Res*. 2020 Dec 15;2020:e5237840.
 38. Siegelaar SE, Hickmann M, Hoekstra JB, Holleman F, DeVries JH. The effect of diabetes on mortality in critically ill patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Crit Care*. 2011;15(5):R205.
 39. Whitcomb BW, Pradhan EK, Pittas AG, Roghmann MC, Perencevich EN. Impact of admission hyperglycemia on hospital mortality in various intensive care unit populations. *Crit Care Med*. 2005 Dec;33(12):2772–7.
 40. Carrasco-Sánchez FJ, López-Carmona MD, Martínez-Marcos FJ, Pérez-Belmonte LM, Hidalgo-Jiménez A, Buonaiuto V, et al. Admission hyperglycaemia as a predictor of mortality in patients hospitalized with COVID-19 regardless of diabetes status: data from the Spanish SEMI-COVID-19 Registry. *Ann Med*. 2021 Jan 1;53(1):103–16.
 41. Freire AX, Bridges L, Umpierrez GE, Kuhl D, Kitabchi AE. Admission Hyperglycemia and Other Risk Factors as Predictors of Hospital Mortality in a Medical ICU Population. *Chest*. 2005 Nov;128(5):3109–16.
 42. Robba C, Bilotta F. Admission hyperglycemia and outcome in ICU patients with sepsis. *J Thorac Dis*. 2016 Jul;8(7):E581–3.
 43. Roberts GW, Quinn SJ, Valentine N, Alhawassi T, O'Dea H, Stranks SN, et al. Relative Hyperglycemia, a Marker of Critical Illness: Introducing the Stress Hyperglycemia Ratio. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2015 Dec;100(12):4490–7.
 44. Koraćević G, Zdravković M. WHAT IS STRESS HYPERGLYCEMIA? A SUGGESTION FOR AN IMPROVEMENT OF ITS DEFINITION. *Acta Endocrinol Buchar*. 2021;17(4):548–51.
 45. Bellaver P, Schaeffer AF, Dullius DP, Viana MV, Leitão CB, Rech TH. Association of multiple glycemic parameters at intensive care unit admission with mortality and clinical outcomes in critically ill patients. *Sci Rep*. 2019 Dec 6;9(1):18498.
 46. Bar-Or D, Rael LT, Madayag RM, Banton KL, Tanner A, Acuna DL, et al. Stress Hyperglycemia in Critically Ill Patients: Insight Into Possible Molecular Pathways. *Front Med [Internet]*. 2019 [cited 2022 Dec 6];6. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmed.2019.00054>
 47. Barmanray RD, Cheuk N, Furlanos S, Greenberg PB, Colman PG, Worth LJ. In-hospital hyperglycemia but not diabetes mellitus alone is associated with increased in-hospital mortality in community-acquired pneumonia (CAP): a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies prior to COVID-19. *BMJ Open Diabetes Res Care*. 2022 Jul 1;10(4):e002880.
 48. Cui C, Zhou M, Cheng L, Ye T, Zhang Y, Zhu F, et al. Admission hyperglycemia as an independent predictor of long-term prognosis in acute myocardial infarction patients without diabetes: A retrospective study. *J Diabetes Investig*. 2021 Jul;12(7):1244–51.
 49. Kerby JD, Griffin RL, MacLennan P, Rue LW. Stress-induced hyperglycemia, not diabetic hyperglycemia, is associated with higher mortality in trauma. *Ann Surg*. 2012 Sep;256(3):446–52.
 50. Dickerson RN, Andromalos L, Brown JC, Correia MITD, Pritts W, Ridley EJ, et al. Obesity and critical care nutrition: current practice gaps and directions for future research. *Crit Care*. 2022 Sep 20;26(1):283.
 51. Decruyenaere A, Steen J, Colpaert K, Benoit DD, Decruyenaere J, Vansteelandt S. The obesity paradox in critically ill patients: a causal learning approach to a casual finding. *Crit Care*. 2020 Aug 5;24(1):485.
 52. Schetz M, De Jong A, Deane AM, Druml W, Hemelaer P, Pelosi P, et al. Obesity in the critically ill: a narrative review. *Intensive Care Med*. 2019 Jun;45(6):757–69.
 53. Földi M, Farkas N, Kiss S, Zádori N, Váncsa S, Szakó L, et al. Obesity is a risk factor for developing critical condition in COVID-19 patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Obes Rev*. 2020;21(10):e13095.
 54. Sjögren L, Stenberg E, Thuccani M, Martikainen J, Rylander C, Wallenius V, et al. Impact of obesity on intensive care outcomes in patients with COVID-19 in Sweden—A cohort study. *PLOS ONE*. 2021 Oct 13;16(10):e0257891.
 55. Akinnusi ME, Pineda LA, El Solh AA. Effect of obesity on intensive care morbidity and mortality: a meta-analysis. *Crit Care Med*. 2008 Jan;36(1):151–8.